

1 Optimization of rice straw pretreatment with 1-ethyl-3- 2 methylimidazolium acetate by the response surface method

3 Helena Poy, Estela Lladosa, Carmen Gabaldón, Sonia Loras*

4 *Address correspondence to Sonia Loras, Sonia.loras@uv.es

5 Department of Chemical Engineering, Universitat de València, Av. De la Universitat S/N, 46100, Burjassot,
6 Spain.

7 Telephone: +34 9635 43317; Fax: +34 963544898

8 ORCID ID:

9 - Sonia Loras: 0000-0002-3863-2201

10 - Carmen Gabaldón: 0000-0003-3136-2269

11 - Estela Lladosa: 0000-0002-8126-1207

14 Abstract

15 Rice straw (RS) is a promising feedstock for transformation into biofuels and bioproducts due to its high
16 sugar content and worldwide availability. However, a pretreatment step is necessary in order to disrupt the
17 RS complex lignocellulosic matrix. The aim of this work was to study RS pretreatment with the ionic liquid
18 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate ([Emim][OAc]) to maximize the enzymatic hydrolysis yield. For this
19 purpose, a response surface method (RSM) based on a central composite design (CCD) was used, with
20 temperature (53-137°C), time (0.3-6.2 hours) and solid loading (3.3-11.7% dry weight) as process variables.
21 The analysis of variance (ANOVA) results suggested that temperature was the most significant factor
22 affecting the fermentable sugar yield of [Emim][OAc] pretreated RS samples. The selected conditions for
23 this pretreatment were 120°C, 5h and 5% (w/w), obtaining 29.8 g/L of potentially fermentable sugars. In
24 these conditions maximum delignification was achieved (64.9%) as well as maximum reduction of the
25 crystallinity index (62.2%), as determined by X-ray diffraction analysis. Fourier-transform infrared
26 spectroscopy (FT-IR) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis were used to confirm the RS
27 amorphous structure after the pretreatment with [Emim][OAc] and showed that it had a more disordered and
28 accessible structure.

29 **Keywords:** Central composite design, enzymatic hydrolysis, ionic liquids, pretreatment, rice straw, 1-ethyl-
30 3-methylimidazolium acetate.

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38 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could
39 have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

40 **Availability of data and material**

41

42 **Code availability**

43

44 **Authors' contributions**

45 **Helena Poy:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Estela Lladosa:**
46 Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review & editing, Supervision. **Carmen Gabaldón:**
47 Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review & editing, Supervision, Project
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58 1. Introduction

59 The depletion of fossil fuel resources and associated environmental pollutions such as climate change
60 and greenhouse gas emissions have increased interest in the search for sustainable and renewable sources of
61 energy [1]. Bio-alcohols can play a vital role in reducing transportation sector emissions [2], highlighting
62 biobutanol produced by biotechnological processes as an advanced biofuel because of its superior properties
63 such as high energy density and its similarity to gasoline [3]. Lignocellulosic biomass consisting of sugars in
64 the form of cellulose and hemicellulose polysaccharides linked with a polyphenolic macromolecule known as
65 lignin is the most renewable source on earth. It is considered a promising feedstock for producing biofuels and
66 bioproducts owing to its availability, low cost, carbon neutrality and high fermentable sugar content [4, 5].
67 Rice straw (RS) is a good candidate for this resource, with an annual production of 600-900 million tons
68 worldwide. RS is mainly composed of cellulose (32–47%), hemicellulose (19–27%) and lignin (5–29%) and
69 other minority compounds such as ash and silica (7.8-20.3%) and extractives (16.1-19.3%) [6]. Due to its
70 recalcitrance, a pretreatment step is crucial to disrupt the complex structure between polysaccharides and
71 lignin, thus increasing the surface area and accessibility to enzymes [7]. Several pretreatment methods *viz.*
72 physical, chemical and biological processes have been developed to enhance the disruption of lignocellulosic
73 materials [8]. However, most of these methods have certain disadvantages, such as severe operating conditions,
74 high energy requirements, high toxicity, formation of inhibitory compounds and loss of fermentable sugar
75 content [9].

76 Currently, the use of ionic liquids (ILs) in pretreatment has received increased attention due to their
77 green properties, besides the ability to dissolve carbohydrates and lignin [10]. ILs are salts consisting entirely
78 of ions with low melting points and special properties including low or negligible vapor pressure, high chemical
79 and thermal stability, non-flammability and recyclability [11]. Their strong hydrogen bonding coordination
80 promotes the alteration of the involved network among carbohydrates and lignin allowing their separation,
81 alongside the minimum formation of degradation products during the process [12]. These solvents are also
82 effective for dissolving cellulose by breaking the hydrogen bonds between its molecular chains through the
83 interaction with cellulose's hydroxyl groups [13]. Dissolved cellulose can be easily regenerated by the addition
84 of an anti-solvent such as water or ethanol [14], exhibiting significantly reduced crystallinity after precipitation
85 [15]. Among the variety of ILs used in pretreatment, 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate ([Emim][OAc]) is
86 recognized as one of the best solvents because it can efficiently dissolve lignocellulosic compounds, besides
87 its biodegradability and relative non-toxicity and non-corrosivity [16, 17]. A broad variety of lignocellulosic
88 substrates have been successfully pretreated using [Emim][OAc], such as Guinea grass [17], *Agave tequilana*
89 Bagasse [18], Aspen wood [19], poplar and switchgrass [20]. Haykir & Bakir [21] demonstrated [Emim][OAc]
90 was better than alkali pretreatment in enhancing enzymatic hydrolysis of pretreated cotton stalks regardless of
91 the substrate loading used, mainly due to its ability to disrupt the crystalline structure.

92 An useful tool for optimization of processing conditions is Central Composite Design (CCD) based
93 on the response surface method (RSM), commonly used to fit empirical second-order polynomial models [22,
94 23]. Although CCD based on RSM could be used to optimize the process variables affecting pretreatment of
95 biomass with ILs, such as temperature, time, solid loading and IL concentration [23–27], this methodology has
96 some drawbacks, such as predicting non-feasible responses. In this context, using physicochemical techniques

97 such as Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and Scanning Electron
98 Microscopy (SEM) may unravel the biomass during IL pretreatment. Combining these structural techniques
99 with the CCD method could help to select the optimal values by providing a better understanding of the
100 molecular mechanism involved.

101 The aim of this work was to study the [Emim][OAc] pretreatment of RS by using RSM in combination
102 with structural techniques. For this purpose, CCD was used to analyze the effect of three processing parameters
103 (temperature, time and solid loading) on the enzymatic hydrolysis yield of [Emim][OAc] pretreated samples
104 and to develop a mathematical model able to adequately predict the process response variable from given input
105 values. The optimal conditions were selected by combining CCD with structural techniques, which are key
106 factors in elucidate the effect of IL on RS.

107 **2. Materials and methods**

108 *2.1 Raw materials and chemicals*

109 RS was acquired from the Albufera Natural Park located near Valencia (Spain). After dried in air, RS
110 was milled and sieved to a particle size between 100-500 μm and then, it was stored in sealed containers at
111 4°C. Before use, it was dried at 45°C. [Emim][OAc] ionic liquid (95% purity by weight) was purchased from
112 IoLiTec (Germany) and used without further purification. The cellulase enzyme blend Cellic® CTec2 was
113 purchased from Novozymes (Denmark) and its cellulase activity (189 FPU/mL) was determined according to
114 the protocol of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [28]. All chemicals needed for RS
115 characterization such as sulfuric acid (98% purity by weight) and ethanol (96% purity by weight) were
116 purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA).

117 *2.2 Ionic liquid pretreatment*

118 Pretreatment was carried out by mixing RS and [Emim][OAc] at different solid loadings in 60 mL
119 Ace Glass pressure tubes (Model 8648-137, Ace Glass, USA). 3.30 g of RS was used in each experiment with
120 the corresponding quantity of IL. The pressure tube was then placed in an orbital shaker (Rotatorm 300045,
121 Selecta, Spain) and heated to the desired temperature (52-137°C) for a certain time (0.3-6.2 hours), with an
122 agitation rate of 100 rpm. At the end of the pretreatment, pressure tubes were submerged in a glass containing
123 cool water to stop the extraction, and 10 mL of deionized water was added to the RS-IL mixture to regenerate
124 the dissolved polysaccharides. The biomass slurry was vigorously washed with deionized water and the solid
125 fraction was separated by vacuum filtration. The remaining IL was removed by washing the filters and the
126 filtrate solids were dried at 105°C and stored at 4°C in sealed containers. The absence of [Emim][OAc] in solid
127 pretreated samples was confirmed by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR).

128 *2.3 Enzymatic hydrolysis*

129 Untreated and [Emim][OAc] pretreated RS samples were subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis in 100
130 mL conical flasks on a shaking incubator (Model G25, New Brunswick Scientific, USA) using Cellic CTec2
131 commercial enzyme blend. A biomass loading of 5% (w/v) and an enzyme dosage of 20 FPU/g dry biomass
132 were used. All the hydrolysis assays were performed with 50 mM sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.0) at 50°C and
133 150 rpm for 72 hours. After enzymatic hydrolysis, the reaction mixture was centrifuged (Centrifuge 5804,

134 Eppendorf, Germany) at 4000 rpm for 6 minutes and then vacuum filtered. The hydrolysate liquid fraction was
 135 analyzed for reducing sugars (cellobiose, glucose, xylose and arabinose) and inhibitory compounds (formic
 136 acid, acetic acid, levulinic acid, 5-HMF and furfural) by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).
 137 Fermentable sugar yield (FSY) was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Fermentable sugar yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Reducing sugars released (g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}) \times V_{\text{hydrolysis}}(\text{L})}{\text{Mass of RS hydrolyzed (g)} \times \text{Total sugars in pretreated RS (\%)}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

138 2.4 Characterization of untreated and pretreated rice straw

139 2.4.1 Chemical characterization

140 The chemical composition of untreated and pretreated RS was determined using NREL protocols [29].
 141 RS was dried at 105°C for total solid content quantification [30] and calcined at 575°C for ash determination
 142 [31]. Glucan, xylan, arabinan and lignin contents were determined by two-step acid hydrolysis [32]. Untreated
 143 samples were previously given a two-step Soxhlet extraction with water and ethanol as solvents [33]. Pretreated
 144 samples and untreated-extractives free samples were hydrolyzed with 72% sulfuric acid at 30°C for 2 hours
 145 with stirring in a water bath (Unitronic, Selecta, Spain). The acid was then diluted to 4% (w/w) by adding
 146 deionized water and the reaction mixture was further hydrolyzed at 121°C for 1 hour in an autoclave (MED 20,
 147 Selecta, Spain). After filtration, the solid fraction was calcinated to quantify acid insoluble lignin (AIL) while
 148 the liquid fraction was used to determine acid soluble lignin (ASL) by UV-vis spectrophotometry (SpectroFlex
 149 6600, WTW, Germany) and sugars by HPLC (Agilent 1100 Series, Agilent Technologies, USA). To determine
 150 reducing sugars, hydrolyzed samples were previously neutralized by calcium carbonate and filtered through a
 151 0.2µm syringe filter. Monomeric sugars were analyzed using RID detector and an Aminex HPX-87H column
 152 (Bio-Rad, Richmond, CA, USA) at 35°C using 5 mM sulfuric acid as mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min.
 153 The glucan, xylan and arabinan contents were calculated from their monomeric concentrations, multiplying by
 154 an anhydrous factor of 0.9 for glucose and 0.88 for xylose and arabinose [32]. Inhibitory content of hydrolyzed
 155 samples was also determined by HPLC using a DAD detector. Acetic, levulinic and formic acids were analyzed
 156 at 210 nm while furfural and 5-HMF were analyzed at 280 nm. The pretreatment efficiency was assessed in
 157 terms of:

$$\text{Sugar recovery (\%)} = \frac{\% \text{Sugar in pretreated RS} \cdot \% \text{Solid recovery}}{\% \text{Sugar in untreated RS}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Delignification (\%)} = 100 - \frac{\% \text{Lignin in pretreated RS} \cdot \% \text{Solid recovery}}{\% \text{Lignin in untreated RS}} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Ash losses (\%)} = 100 - \frac{\% \text{Ash in pretreated RS} \cdot \% \text{Solid recovery}}{\% \text{Ash in untreated RS}} \quad (4)$$

158 2.4.2 Structural analysis

159 FT-IR analyses of untreated and pretreated samples were carried out to determine chemical changes
 160 in the RS structure. These analyses were conducted in an ATR-FTIR spectrometer (ATR Agilent Cary 630

161 FTIR spectrometer, Agilent, USA). Sample spectra were obtained in duplicate using 64 scans per sample over
 162 the range of 400-4000 cm^{-1} with a spectral resolution of 2 cm^{-1} . The effects of pretreatment on the RS
 163 morphology were analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (S-4800, Hitachi, Japan) operating at an
 164 acceleration voltage of 10 kV. Untreated and [Emim][OAc]-pretreated RS samples were sputter-coated with
 165 gold-paladium before SEM analysis. Surface morphology images of some RS samples were acquired at a
 166 magnification of 35X, 180X and 500X. Changes in crystallinity after pretreatment were analyzed by X-ray
 167 powder diffractometry (XRD). XRD measurements were performed on a Bruker D8 Advance A25 X-Ray
 168 Diffractometer (Bruker, USA) equipped with Cu radiation ($\lambda=1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). Samples were scanned over the
 169 angular range of 5-60°, with a step size of 0.02° and step time of 1s. The crystallinity index (CrI) of the samples
 170 was calculated by the peak intensity method [34] as:

$$\text{CrI} = \left(\frac{I_{002} - I_{\text{am}}}{I_{002}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

171 where I_{002} is the maximum diffraction peak intensity of plane 002 (at around $2\theta = 22.1^\circ$) and I_{am} is the
 172 amorphous peak at around $2\theta = 18.7^\circ$.

173 2.5 Experimental design and statistical analysis

174 A response surface method (RSM) based on a Central Composite Design (CCD) was applied to study
 175 the effect of pretreatment conditions (temperature, time and solid loading) on the response variable selected:
 176 Fermentable sugar yield (FSY). For this purpose, the commercial software Minitab 19.1 (Minitab Inc., USA)
 177 was used. The experimental design included five levels of the three independent variables for a total of twenty
 178 runs with six replicates at the central point (Table 1). The experimental results were fitted into a second-order
 179 polynomial regression model as shown in Eq. (7):

$$y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \beta_i x_i + \sum_{i=1}^3 \beta_{ii} x_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=i+1}^3 \beta_{ij} x_i x_j \quad (6)$$

180 where y is the response variable (FSY), x_i is the independent variable (temperature, time and solid loading), β_0
 181 is the constant coefficient, β_i is the linear coefficient, β_{ii} is the quadratic coefficient, and β_{ij} is the ij interaction
 182 coefficient.

183 Evaluation of each coefficient of the model was statistically processed by analysis of variance
 184 (ANOVA) at the significance level of $p=0.05$. Assessment of the model was based on the R-squared value (R^2)
 185 and model p -value. Its validation was carried out by four replicates of the experiment that achieve the best
 186 conditions for [Emim][OAc] pretreatment of RS.

187 3. Results and discussion

188 3.1 Effects of pretreatment on rice straw recovery and composition

189 Chemical composition and solid recovery of untreated and pretreated RS, as well as sugar recoveries,
 190 delignification and ash losses are summarized in Table 2. Untreated RS contained $35.8 \pm 2.1\%$ glucan, $14.8 \pm$
 191 1.6% xylan, $2.7 \pm 0.4\%$ arabinan, $14.3 \pm 0.3\%$ lignin, $13.2 \pm 2.1\%$ extractives and $16.7 \pm 0.1\%$ ashes (w/w).
 192 Compared to other RS batches reported elsewhere [4, 35], the RS of this study showed a greater susceptibility
 193 for its sugars exploitation due its lower lignin content, which is known to increase the recalcitrance of

194 lignocellulosic material hindering accessibility to enzymes. After pretreatment, all the RS samples showed
195 mass losses due to the capacity of [Emim][OAc] to extract biomass components. Despite the loss of material,
196 particularly sugars, extensive washing was required, as any remaining IL could deactivate enzymes and inhibit
197 microorganisms during the enzymatic hydrolysis and fermentation steps [36]. The percentage of recovered
198 solids varied from 62.9% to 95.2%. Generally, solid recovery decreased with increases in temperature and
199 time, also with decreases in solid loading, although temperature had a stronger effect. At higher temperatures,
200 recovery of biomass components decreased, but biomass dissolution and swelling increased [24]. Likewise,
201 significant amounts of sugars were lost after pretreating RS with [Emim][OAc], although the sugar content had
202 been enriched in some pretreated solids (Runs 2 and 7). Glucan recovery after pretreatment varied in the range
203 from 57.6% to 79.5%, while xylan and arabinan recovery varied between 54.8% to 100% and 57.9% to 89.6%,
204 respectively. Although these values are strongly influenced by temperature as solid recovery, a fraction of
205 sugars was lost in the water washing step due to the weaker bond between cellulose and hemicellulose. Li et
206 al. [37] studied the effect of washing [Emim][OAc] pretreated switchgrass in sugar losses carrying out seven
207 different successive washes, showing that sugar losses increased with the number of washes, especially in the
208 case of the hemicellulose fraction due to its loss of bonding with the biomass structure.

209 Lignin is the main obstacle to enzymatic hydrolysis, since it acts as a barrier against enzymatic attack
210 on carbohydrates, giving resistance and rigidity to the lignocellulosic structure [38]. Delignification after
211 [Emim][OAc] pretreatment varied in the range from 0.8% to 64.9%, increasing with temperature as a result of
212 better lignin dissolution. At low temperatures, delignification was insignificant, achieving only 0.8% of lignin
213 removal for the experiment at 53 °C (Run 12). The maximum delignification (64.9%) was reached at 120 °C
214 for 5 hours with 5% (w/w) solid loading (Run 7). Higher temperatures usually accelerate lignin solubilization
215 in IL and dissolved lignin would remain in solution when an antisolvent, such as water, was added for
216 regeneration and washing processes [39, 40]. Weerachanchai et al. [41] also proved the suitability of
217 [Emim][OAc] as delignifying solvent for rice straw, obtaining a similar maximum delignification of 63% at
218 120 °C with 5% (w/w) of solid loading, but for 24 hours instead of the 5 hours employed in this work. Fockink
219 et al. [42] studied the best conditions to delignificate cotton residues with [Emim][OAc], yielding a similar
220 degree of delignification (62.9%) but requiring a high temperature (160 °C) with a 3-hours reaction by using
221 10% (w/w) solid loading. Odorico et al. [17] obtained a lower delignification degree (20.5%) during
222 pretreatment of Guinea grass with [Emim][OAc] at 157 °C, 0.5 h and 14% (w/w) solid loading, which could
223 have been directly influenced by the higher solid loading used, thus negatively impacting the solid-liquid mass
224 transfer.

225 Ash removal is important since silica, the main component of RS ash, like lignin, blocks cellulitic
226 enzymes. Silica can adsorb cellulases by electrostatic interactions and/or hydrogen bonding, reducing the
227 number of active sites on the cellulase surface, thus requiring a higher enzyme dosage, which raises operating
228 costs [43, 44]. In this study, ash losses varied in the range between 30-40%, with higher values achieved at
229 higher temperatures. However, pretreated RS samples still had a significant amount of ash and its impact was
230 evaluated in the enzymatic hydrolysis stage.

231 *3.2 Effects of pretreatment on enzymatic hydrolysis*

232 Untreated and [Emim][OAc] pretreated RS samples were subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis and
233 results are summarized in Table 3. Without pretreatment, fermentable sugar yield (FSY) of RS was only 19%,
234 which corresponds to 22.7%, 10.1% and 7.0% of glucose, xylose and arabinose yield, respectively.
235 Saccharification yield after [Emim][OAc] pretreatment was improved in all the cases analyzed, varying in the
236 30.7-98.3% range. Generally, hydrolysis yield increases with temperature as a result of a more open and
237 accessible structure. Similar patterns were observed for glucose and hemicelluloses digestibilities, however,
238 higher values were obtained for glucose yields since the enzyme complex used contains mostly cellulase-type
239 enzymes. The maximum sugar yield obtained was 98.3% (120 °C, 5 h, 5 % (w/w), run 7) corresponding to 29.8
240 g/L of potentially fermentable sugars. In this run the cellulose fraction was totally hydrolyzed, indicating the
241 excellent susceptibility of RS to enzymatic attack after [Emim][OAc] pretreatment under these conditions.
242 These results were even better than those reported by Poornejad et al. [45] by pretreating rice straw with
243 [Emim][OAc] at 120°C for 5h at 5% (w/w) solid loading, obtaining glucose yields up to 90% after enzymatic
244 hydrolysis. On the other hand, the lowest saccharification yield (31%) was obtained for run 20 (70°C, 1.5h, 5%
245 (w/w)), in which the combination of the low temperature and time was insufficient to deconstruct the RS
246 structure. The enzymatic attack was thus severely limited and enzymatic hydrolysis values were close to those
247 obtained with untreated RS (19%). Overall sugar recovery accounts for the joint evaluation of pretreatment
248 and enzymatic hydrolysis steps, as the loss of material involved is considered for its calculation (Table 3). The
249 same trend was found as for fermentable sugar yield, obtaining the highest overall sugar recovery (70.6%) in
250 run 7 (120 °C, 5 h, 5% (w/w)). Therefore, these conditions can be considered the best exploitation of raw
251 material as regards both from the overall and enzymatic hydrolysis processes.

252 Inhibitory content after enzymatic hydrolysis was evaluated by HPLC. Levulinic acid and furfural
253 were not detected in any samples, while 5-HMF was only detected in some samples (runs 2,7,9 and 11) at very
254 low concentrations (< 3 mg/L). These values are favorable for ABE fermentation, since the reported inhibitory
255 concentrations of furfural and 5-HMF were 0.3 and 0.6 g/L, respectively [46]. Formic acid was detected in all
256 samples at very low concentrations (0.07-1.13 g/L) while inhibitory levels were reported to be greater than 0.5
257 g/L [47]. Acetic acid was the principal sugar degradation product obtained after enzymatic hydrolysis of
258 pretreated samples, promoted by the hydrolysis of acetyl groups of hemicelluloses. Acetic acid concentrations
259 varied in the range between 2.3-4.15 g/L, typical concentration values found in enzymatic hydrolysis studies
260 of pretreated rice straw [48]. Wang et al. [49] demonstrated that an acetic acid concentration of 90 mM (5.4
261 g/L) had no influence on ABE fermentation by *Clostridium acetobutylicum* DSM 1731. In fact, it has been
262 reported that acetic acid concentrations above 3 g/L can improve ABE production by *Clostridium beijerinckii*
263 DSM 6422 [50]. IL pretreatment produces limited quantities of inhibitors, although minor amounts of IL in
264 pretreated samples are potentially toxic to enzymes and microorganisms [51]. Ninomiya et al. [52] proved that
265 a concentration of 16% [Emim][OAc] (w/w) could reduce the activity of Cellic® CTec2 by 50%, while only
266 an [Emim][OAc] concentration of 0.6% (w/w) was sufficient to reduce the relative yeast growth in a culture
267 with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* by 50%. The high fermentable sugar yields achieved in our study (>85% in
268 runs 1,2,7 and 10) confirmed the proper washing procedure during [Emim][OAc] pretreatment despite the loss
269 of sugars in pretreated samples.

270 *3.3 Statistical analysis of response surfaces*

271 The influence of temperature, time and solid loading on fermentable sugar yield (FSY) was studied
272 by RSM based on a CCD. The experimental data shown in Table 3 were used to determine the regression
273 coefficients of the second-order polynomial model (Eq. 7) and the model predicted values for the variable
274 response as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 275 \text{FSY (\%)} &= 135.0 - 1.51 \cdot \text{Temperature} + 1.9 \cdot \text{time} - 12.35 \cdot \text{Solid loading} + 0.01274 \cdot \text{Temperature}^2 + 1.224 \\ 276 &\cdot \text{time}^2 + 1.091 \cdot \text{Solid Loading}^2 - 0.0026 \cdot \text{Temperature} \cdot \text{time} - 0.0265 \cdot \text{Temperature} \cdot \text{Solid loading} - 1.045 \\ 277 &\cdot \text{time} \cdot \text{Solid loading} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

278 The analysis of variance (ANOVA) results and the coded regression coefficients for the second order
279 model calculated are shown in Table 4. The ANOVA results indicate that the model was statistically significant
280 ($p < 0.05$) under 95% of confidence level, whereas lack-of-fit was insignificant relative to the pure error,
281 indicating the goodness of the fitted regression. Furthermore, the correlation coefficient (R^2) was
282 approximately 84%, which implied that a 16% of the total variability could not be explained by the regression
283 model. The good correlation between the calculated and experimental values can be seen in Figure S1
284 (Supplementary Material). The value of adjusted R^2 of 70% and the standard deviation of 11% also suggested
285 that the model adequately predicted the response. Considering ANOVA results, the linear coefficient of
286 temperature (A) and the quadratic coefficients of temperature (A^2) and solid loading (C^2) were found to be
287 significant for FSY. Based on the fitted quadratic model proposed, three-dimensional response surface plots
288 were generated to examine the interactive effects between any two process pretreatment variables on the
289 response (Figure 1 a-b). As illustrated in Fig. 1, the response surface plots indicate that temperature was the
290 main factor influencing fermentable sugar yield. It can be seen that FSY increased with temperature, regardless
291 of time and solid loading used in the pretreatment process. The higher saccharification yield at higher
292 temperatures could be attributed to several factors. On the one hand, the solubility of lignocellulosic
293 components increases with temperature, resulting in a higher delignification and cellulose dissolution, which
294 is subsequently regenerated in a weaker, more amorphous material and more accessible to enzyme attack. On
295 the other hand, [Emim][OAc] viscosity decreases with increasing temperature, which boosts biomass-IL
296 mixing and mass/heat transfer. In addition to temperature and temperature squared, solid loading squared was
297 also found to be significant for FSY according to the ANOVA test. However, solid loading squared had not
298 as much influence on FSY as the temperature parameters, as reflected in its lower F-value and coded
299 coefficient. Solid loading shows to be of importance in achieving high fermentable sugar yields due to the
300 higher efficiency in biomass dissolution, although in terms of overall mass balance, its effect is negligible.

301 According to the fitted second-order model developed, the optimum values for pretreatment
302 conditions predicted were 137 °C, 6.2 h and 3.3% (w/w) solid loading, which corresponds to the extreme values
303 of the three parameters tested. However, the statistical model developed showed a limited ability to predict
304 optimum values as overpredicted the saccharification yield (161.6%). To determine the best conditions to
305 enhance enzymatic hydrolysis of RS pretreated with [Emim][OAc], the structural characterizations of the most
306 promising runs (2 and 7) as well as the worst (run 20) in terms of fermentable sugar yield were carried out in
307 order to additionally consider the effect of [Emim][OAc] on the RS structure for selecting the best operational
308 conditions.

309

310 3.4 Structural characterization

311 3.4.1 FT-IR analysis

312 Untreated and [Emim][OAc] pretreated RS samples (runs 2,7 and 20) were characterized by FT-IR to
313 study the structural changes after pretreatment (Figure 2). The most significant structural changes were
314 appreciated for the spectra from run 7, while the least modifications were observed in run 20. The band at 3330
315 cm^{-1} representing OH stretching is displaced to higher intensities in pretreated samples, indicating an increase
316 in the free hydroxyl groups and reduced inter molecular hydrogen bonding [53]. The spectra at 1430 and 897
317 cm^{-1} represent crystalline cellulose I and amorphous cellulose II, respectively [26, 45]. After pretreatment, the
318 bands at 1430 cm^{-1} were reduced, while those at 897 cm^{-1} became more intense, which means that
319 [Emim][OAc] pretreatment reduces cellulose crystallinity. In pretreated RS samples, peak at 1050 cm^{-1} which
320 is indicative of C-O stretching in carbohydrates, decreases its intensity, indicating that highly ordered hydrogen
321 bonds in untreated RS have been removed due to cellulose dissolution and regeneration in pretreatment [54].
322 This dissolution was not significant for pretreatment at 70°C (run 20), confirming that this temperature is not
323 high enough to attack RS cellulose. The band at 1734 cm^{-1} , which represents ester bonds linking acetyl and p-
324 coumaryl of hemicellulose and lignin, was also reduced after pretreatment, implying the breaking of ester
325 linkages between these components [53]. Absorption peaks at 2852, 2925 and 2935 cm^{-1} are characteristic of
326 lignin structure, corresponding to symmetric and asymmetric CH stretching of CH_3 , CH_2 and CH, softened
327 after pretreatment, probably due to lignin depolymerization by [Emim][OAc] [55]. The peak at 1600 cm^{-1}
328 (stretching of aromatic benzene ring in lignin) was practically disappeared in pretreated biomass, indicating
329 partial removal of lignin [56]. The peaks at 1328 and 835 cm^{-1} are also associated with lignin, representing
330 syringyl and guaiacyl units [57], which are less intensive in pretreated rice straw indicating again the partial
331 removal of lignin after [Emim][OAc] pretreatment, especially at 120°C, 5 hours and 5% (w/w) solid loading
332 (Run 7), which corresponded to the highest delignification achieved.

333 3.4.2 SEM analysis

334 Morphological changes on the RS surface after pretreatment were examined by SEM images (Fig.3).
335 Untreated RS (Figs. 3a-c) presented a highly ordered, packed and inaccessible structure, with well-defined
336 fibres and particulate material on the surface. This particulate material are silica proper of ashes, which restrict
337 enzymatic hydrolysis of sugars [45]. Because of the particle size reduction before pretreatment, raw RS showed
338 mechanical damage in its structure (Fig 3a) [18]. After [Emim][OAc] pretreatment, no significant changes in
339 morphology were observed in the sample corresponding to run 20 (70°C, 1.5h, 5% w/w) (Figs 3d-f), confirming
340 again that these conditions are not sufficient severe to disrupt the lignocellulosic matrix. However, this
341 pretreated RS sample showed signs of a slightly disordered structure, although not enough to substantially
342 improve the enzymatic hydrolysis performance. Structural alterations were clearly seen in the samples
343 corresponding at run 2 (137°C, 3.3h, 7.5% solid loading) (Figs 3 j-l) and run 7 (120°C, 5h, 5% solid loading)
344 (Figs 3 g-i), where original RS structure was completely lost. In both samples a disordered and conglomerated
345 structure was observed, which was turned into an amorphous and porous form as a result of [Emim][OAc]
346 pretreatment. Moreover, no fibres were found in these samples and the particulate material associated with
347 silica and ash was also partially removed, especially in the case of run 7 (Figs. 3 g-i). These results indicated
348 that [Emim][OAc] pretreatment at temperatures up to 120°C could reduce RS recalcitrance, leaving a

349 homogeneous structure and an accessible surface area. As a consequence, all sugars were almost completely
350 hydrolyzed in both samples.

351 3.4.3 XRD analysis

352 X-Ray Diffraction was used to study changes in crystallinity after [Emim][OAc] pretreatment. XRD
353 patterns of untreated and three pretreated RS samples are shown in Fig.4. Untreated biomass presents two
354 characteristics cellulose peaks at angles of 15 and 22.1°, corresponding to the (001) and (002) lattice planes of
355 crystalline cellulose I, respectively [58]. Cellulose I is more resistant to cellulase hydrolysis than cellulose II
356 because the van der Waals interactions between hydrogen-bonded layers of cellulose I are stronger than those
357 in cellulose II [59]. After [Emim][OAc] pretreatment, the maximum peak at 22° was shifted to a lower angle
358 (~21°), indicating that cellulose I became more amorphous and transitioned to cellulose II. This alteration
359 commonly occurs in biomass samples pretreated with ILs containing anions that are good hydrogen bond
360 acceptors, as in the case of [Emim][OAc] [42]. The peak at 15° lost intensity in pretreated samples from runs
361 2 and 7, suggesting that in these cases, more cellulose had been attacked during [Emim][OAc] pretreatment.
362 Conversion of cellulose I to cellulose II was also confirmed by calculating the crystallinity index (CrI) of
363 analyzed samples from XRD data. Untreated RS had a CrI of 50.66%, indicating a highly crystalline structure.
364 As can be seen in Table 5, the CrI of pretreated samples was reduced in all the cases analyzed in the range of
365 34-62%, which directly affected enzymatic hydrolysis yield. A reduced crystallinity index results in a more
366 amorphous cellulose, so that, higher saccharification yields were obtained for pretreated RS than untreated
367 samples. The highest crystallinity index reduction (62.2%) was obtained in run 7, which had the highest
368 delignification (64.9%) as well as the most significant structural changes in RS structure were observed (Fig 3
369 g-i). In these conditions, the highest saccharification yields were also obtained, confirming the excellent
370 enzymatic susceptibility of this pretreated material. A slightly higher crystallinity index was obtained for run
371 2, also showing the good enzymatic susceptibility of this pretreated sample, as reflected in the similar
372 fermentable sugar yield.

373 3.5 Selection of pretreatment conditions

374 In this work, a mathematical model was developed to optimize the fermentable sugar yield of RS
375 pretreated with [Emim][OAc]. This model suggested that enzymatic hydrolysis was improved at higher
376 pretreatment temperatures and times and lower solid loadings. To determine the best pretreatment conditions,
377 structural analysis of the most promising runs (2 and 7) were carried out, revealing no notable differences in
378 RS structure between pretreatment temperatures of 120 °C (run 7) and 137 °C (run 2). In fact, delignification
379 and ash losses were higher for the pretreated sample at 120°C (run 7). At temperatures up to 120°C, RS had a
380 completely open and easily hydrolysable structure, since practically all the sugars contained it contained were
381 entirely hydrolyzed. However, at higher temperatures sugar losses were noticeable, as reflected in overall sugar
382 recovery (Table 3), which should be avoided for the economic viability of the biorefinery process. The
383 evaluation of process losses (overall sugar recovery) and susceptibility of pretreated material (FSY) played an
384 important role in fully analyzing joint pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis processes, showing that
385 pretreatment at 120 °C instead of 137 °C represented an advantage in terms of RS sugar recovery. Thus, run 7
386 (120 °C, 5 h, 5% solid loading) was selected as the best conditions to RS pretreatment with [Emim][OAc]. At
387 these selected best conditions fermentable sugar yield was predicted to be 99.2%. Four replicate confirmation

388 experiments were conducted to validate the selected operational parameters. The experimental fermentable
389 sugar yield obtained under the selected conditions was $97.7 \pm 3.3\%$. Differences of less than 2% between
390 experimental and predicted values confirmed the soundness of the model prediction.

391 A comparison of the results obtained with those reported in the literature on similar [Emim][OAc]
392 pretreatment procedures of lignocellulosic substrates is summarized in Table 6. Among the different
393 operational conditions employed in [Emim][OAc] pretreatment, those used in this work obtained the highest
394 delignification. Regarding enzymatic hydrolysis process, many studies focused only on glucose hydrolysis,
395 neglecting the secondary sugar (xylose), which could be of importance in the context of a biorefinery and sugar
396 exploitation. The glucose hydrolysis yield is higher than 90% in all the cases analyzed, showing the potential
397 of [Emim][OAc] in lignocellulosic selective dissolution and the effective attack on crystalline cellulose. Qiu
398 et al. [58] reported a slightly lower glucose yield (87.0%) due to the shorter time used in [Emim][OAc]
399 pretreatment than the other studies analyzed. Similar glucose yields were obtained in [Emim][OAc]
400 pretreatment of Aspen wood in the best conditions reported in this study [19] as well as in palm oil empty fruit
401 bunch pretreatment at a higher temperature (130°C) and shorter time (2h) [60]. Raj et al. [61] concluded that
402 [Emim][OAc] pretreatment of wheat straw at 10% (w/w) solid loading provided better biomass deconstruction
403 at 130 °C for 2 hours than at 100 °C for 5 hours, confirming that temperature is the main factor affecting the
404 pretreatment process. Although similar glucose yields were obtained in this wheat straw pretreatment than in
405 the present work, lower degrees of delignification and xylose yield were achieved than ours. In this regard, the
406 higher solid loading (10% (w/w)) used in wheat straw pretreatment could make lignin extraction difficult, while
407 the higher temperature (130°C) could promote xylose degradation. Alkaline pretreatment is a commonly used
408 pretreatment method of lignocellulosic biomass, since it is relatively cheap and easy to operate [62]. Valles et
409 al. [48] used NaOH 0.75% (w/v) in alkaline pretreatment of rice straw at 134°C for 20 min at 5% (w/w) solid
410 loading, obtaining high fermentable sugar yields (85% and 67% of glucose and xylose yield, respectively),
411 although not as promising as in the reported [Emim][OAc] pretreatments, indicating the superiority of
412 [Emim][OAc] pretreatment.

413 **4. Conclusions**

414 Feasibility of using [Emim][OAc] in rice straw pretreatment was proved in this work, obtaining
415 enhanced biomass digestibility. Structural analysis has been shown as a very useful tool for the better
416 assessment of enzymatic hydrolysis. The best processing conditions selected for [Emim][OAc] pretreatment
417 of RS were determined to be 120 °C, 5 h, 5% (w/w). Under these conditions, nearly all the sugars in pretreated
418 RS were hydrolyzed, whereas the highest delignification (65%) and the most significant structural changes in
419 RS were obtained, showing the suitability of [Emim][OAc] for RS pretreatment. Due to this [Emim][OAc]
420 potential in the biorefinery context, further studies on the recovery and reutilization of this IL should be carried
421 out in order to study the cost-effectiveness of pretreatment process.

422 **5. References**

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Tables: Optimization of rice straw pretreatment with 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate by the response surface method

Table 1 Levels of the pretreatment conditions variables tested in the central composite design (CCD)

Process parameters	Coding	Unit	Levels				
			$-\alpha^*$	-1	0	+1	$+\alpha$
Temperature	A	°C	53.0	70.0	95.0	120.0	137.0
Time	B	Hours	0.3	1.5	3.3	5.0	6.2
Solid loading	C	% (w/w)	3.3	5.0	7.5	10.0	11.7

α^* (axial distance) = $\sqrt[4]{N}$, where N is the number of experiments of the factorial design. In this case, the value of α was 1.6818.

Table 2 Main composition of untreated and [Emim][OAc] pretreated rice straw

Run	Pretreatment variables			Main composition of pretreated RS						Recoveries/Losses after pretreatment				
	Temperature, A (°C)	Time, B (h)	Solid loading, C (% w/w)	Solid recovery (%)	Glucan (%)	Xylan (%)	Arabinan (%)	Lignin (%)	Ash (%)	Glucan recovery (%)	Xylan recovery (%)	Arabinan recovery (%)	Delignification (%)	Ash losses (%)
1	120	5.0	10.0	78.3	35.1	16.6	2.7	11.4	14.5	76.6	87.9	78.1	37.8	32.3
2	137	3.3	7.5	62.9	39.9	12.9	2.5	12.2	17.0	70.0	54.8	58.6	46.3	36.1
3	95	3.3	7.5	82.9	29.7	15.8	2.6	13.2	14.0	68.6	88.5	82.0	23.7	28.5
4	95	0.3	7.5	85.8	24.7	12.8	2.0	14.3	14.0	59.3	74.2	65.3	14.2	28.5
5	70	1.5	10.0	82.8	28.2	15.6	2.4	15.9	13.8	65.2	87.2	73.1	8.1	31.6
6	95	3.3	11.7	95.2	25.7	13.7	2.0	13.8	13.8	68.4	88.2	72.6	8.3	21.6
7	120	5.0	5.0	70.6	36.0	15.5	2.7	7.1	14.5	70.9	74.1	71.1	64.9	38.9
8	120	1.5	5.0	78.9	35.0	18.0	2.9	12.5	13.3	77.2	95.9	85.2	31.4	37.3
9	95	6.2	7.5	80.1	32.7	16.9	2.6	9.9	13.7	73.0	91.7	78.4	44.5	34.5
10	95	3.3	3.3	77.6	26.7	12.7	2.0	14.0	14.1	57.9	66.5	57.9	24.4	34.7
11	95	3.3	7.5	78.6	32.3	16.9	2.6	12.8	14.1	70.8	90.0	77.1	29.8	33.8
12	53	3.3	7.5	85.8	24.0	12.8	1.9	16.6	13.7	57.6	74.4	62.7	0.8	29.6
13	120	1.5	10.0	78.0	34.7	17.1	2.8	13.2	14.3	75.5	90.4	82.0	28.4	33.4
14	70	5.0	5.0	94.6	22.9	12.2	1.9	13.2	12.0	60.4	77.8	67.6	13.1	32.1
15	95	3.3	7.5	84.8	32.1	16.9	2.6	13.3	13.4	76.0	97.1	83.1	21.1	31.9
16	95	3.3	7.5	78.8	35.8	18.4	2.9	13.1	13.8	78.8	97.9	86.8	28.0	35.0
17	95	3.3	7.5	80.9	29.9	16.0	2.5	13.3	13.5	67.5	87.4	75.8	25.0	34.8
18	70	5.0	10.0	90.3	31.6	17.1	2.6	14.4	13.2	79.5	104.7	89.3	9.0	28.6
19	95	3.3	7.5	81.5	34.8	18.6	2.9	16.1	13.8	79.1	102.7	89.6	8.2	32.9
20	70	1.5	5.0	90.7	30.9	16.0	2.2	15.6	12.8	78.2	98.4	76.2	1.1	30.7
Untreated	-	-	-	100.0	35.8	14.8	2.7	14.3	16.7	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3 Enzymatic digestibility of untreated and [Emim][OAc] pretreated RS samples

Run	Pretreatment variables			Enzymatic hydrolysis: concentrations and yields									
	Temperature, A (°C)	Time, B (h)	Solid loading, C (% w/w)	Cellobiose (g/L)	Glucose (g/L)	Xylose (g/L)	Arabinose (g/L)	Total fermentable sugars (g/L)	Glucose yield (%)	Xylose yield (%)	Arabinose yield (%)	Fermentable sugar yield (%)	Overall sugar recovery ^a (%)
1	120	5.0	10.0	0.8	17.6	7.3	0.6	26.4	90.4	77.9	37.8	86.7	69.3
2	137	3.3	7.5	0.8	22.1	6.0	0.8	29.8	99.8	81.9	56.8	96.6	62.9
3	95	3.3	7.5	0.4	10.5	4.6	0.3	15.9	63.9	51.6	20.9	59.1	44.2
4	95	0.3	7.5	0.4	10.8	3.3	0.3	14.7	78.2	45.5	22.1	66.4	42.3
5	70	1.5	10.0	0.3	8.6	2.2	0.2	11.4	55.1	25.3	13.3	44.1	31.7
6	95	3.3	11.7	0.4	8.6	3.7	0.0	12.7	59.8	48.0	3.8	54.8	40.7
7	120	5.0	5.0	0.6	21.0	7.3	0.8	29.8	105.2	82.7	50.9	98.3	70.6
8	120	1.5	5.0	0.7	17.2	6.3	0.5	24.8	88.5	61.8	29.2	79.1	65.5
9	95	6.2	7.5	0.5	11.5	5.1	0.5	17.6	63.3	52.9	30.7	60.3	47.3
10	95	3.3	3.3	0.5	14.9	4.8	0.3	20.7	100.6	67.3	28.1	89.2	53.8
11	95	3.3	7.5	0.3	9.2	4.1	0.4	14.0	51.2	42.1	23.8	48.1	36.8
12	53	3.3	7.5	0.4	9.0	2.1	0.2	11.7	67.6	28.4	14.8	53.9	33.7
13	120	1.5	10.0	0.6	17.0	6.4	0.6	24.6	88.1	65.3	38.2	80.3	64.3
14	70	5.0	5.0	0.4	8.6	2.4	0.2	11.6	67.5	34.9	16.4	55.9	36.7
15	95	3.3	7.5	0.3	8.0	2.5	0.2	10.9	44.8	25.7	12.1	37.8	31.1
16	95	3.3	7.5	0.3	10.2	3.4	0.2	14.2	51.2	32.8	14.3	44.4	37.5
17	95	3.3	7.5	0.3	9.5	2.9	0.2	13.0	57.0	32.3	14.6	47.9	35.2
18	70	5.0	10.0	0.4	9.8	2.7	0.2	13.1	56.0	27.4	12.2	45.4	39.6
19	95	3.3	7.5	0.4	12.9	4.1	0.3	17.7	66.5	39.2	17.0	56.2	48.5
20	70	1.5	5.0	0.3	5.7	2.4	0.1	8.5	33.1	26.0	5.1	30.7	25.7
Untreated				0.2	4.5	0.9	0.1	5.7	22.7	10.1	7.0	19.0	19.0

^aConsidering sugar content in raw RS.

Table 4 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the quadratic model (fermentable sugar yield)

Source	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean square	F-value	p-value Prob > F	Coefficient ^a
Model	6380.64	9	708.96	5.93	0.005	
Lineal	4663.39	3	1554.46	12.99	0.001	49.10
A - Temperature	4224.92	1	4224.92	35.32	< 0.0001	17.59
B- Time	128.21	1	128.21	1.07	0.325	3.06
C – Solid loading	310.26	1	310.26	2.59	0.138	-4.77
Square	1527.92	3	509.31	4.26	0.035	
A ²	914.15	1	914.15	7.64	0.0200	7.96
B ²	202.43	1	202.43	1.69	0.222	3.75
C ²	669.46	1	669.46	5.60	0.040	6.82
2-way interaction	189.33	3	63.11	0.53	0.673	
AB	0.10	1	0.10	0.00	0.977	-0.11
AC	21.93	1	21.93	0.18	0.678	-1.66
BC	167.30	1	167.30	1.40	0.264	-4.57
Residual	1196.22	10	119.62			
Lack of fit	893.91	5	178.78	2.96	0.130	
Pure error	302.31	5	60.46			

R-squared = 84.21; Adj. R-squared = 70.00; Std. dev = 10.94%

^aFor coded values.

Table 5 Crystallinity index of untreated and [Emim][OAc] pretreated samples

Run	Pretreatment conditions			CrI (%)
	T(°C)	t (h)	Solid loading (%w/w)	
Untreated	-	-	-	50.7
2	137	3.3	7.5	23.2
7	120	5.0	5.0	19.2
20	70	1.5	5.0	33.5

Table 6 Comparison of [Emim][OAc] pretreatments of different lignocellulosic substrates

Lignocellulosic substrate	Type of pretreatment	Pretreatment conditions			Enzymatic hydrolysis			Delignification	Reference
		Temperature	time	Solid loading	Biomass loading	Enzyme loading	Hydrolysis yield* (%)		
Energy cane bagasse	[Emim][OAc]	120 °C	30 min	5% (w/w)	1% (w/v)	Spezyme CP (30 FPU/g glucan) Novozyme 188 (30 CBU/g glucan)	87% cellulose yield 64.3% hemicellulose yield	32.0 (%)	[58]
Aspen wood	[Emim][OAc]	120 °C	5h	5% (w/w)	3% (w/v)	Celluclast 1.5L (20 FPU/g glucan) Novozyme 188 (30 CBU/g glucan)	95.4% glucose yield	**	[19]
Oil palm empty fruit bunch	[Emim][OAc]	130 °C	2h	5% (w/w)	5% (w/v)	Celluclast 1.5L (30 FPU/g glucan) Novozyme 188 (1/3 (v/v) of Celluclast 1.5L)	95.5% glucose yield	52.6 (%)	[60]
Wheat straw	[Emim][OAc]	130°C	2h	10% (w/w)	10% (w/v)	SacchariSEBC6 (10 FPU/g biomass)	98.7% glucose yield 42% xylose yield	51.0 (%)	[61]
Rice straw	Microwave assisted hydrothermolysis	200°C	40 min	10% (w/w)	10% (w/v)	Cellic CTec2 (4.1FPU/g biomass)	44.5% glucose yield 44.9% xylose yield	13.3%	[62]
Rice straw	Organosolv (75%w/v EtOH containing 1%w/w H ₂ SO ₄ as catalyst)	180°C	30 min	12.5% (w/w)	5% (w/v)	Celluclast 1.5L (25 FPU/g biomass) Novozyme 188 (40 IU/g biomass)	46.2% glucose yield 40.4% xylose yield	64.2%	[63]
Rice straw	Alkali (0.75%w/v NaOH)	134°C	20 min	5%(w/w)	8% (w/v)	Cellic CTec2 (15FPU/g biomass)	85% glucose yield 67% xylose yield	45.6%	[48]
Rice straw	[Emim][OAc]	120 °C	5h	5% (w/w)	5% (w/v)	Cellic Ctec2 (20FPU/g biomass)	100% glucose yield 82% xylose yield	65.0 (%)	This study

*Calculated based on total glucose/xylose present in pretreated biomass.

**Not indicated

Figures: Optimization of rice straw pretreatment with 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate by the response surface method

Fig. 1 Three-dimensional response surface plots of interaction effects of two independent variables on fermentable sugar yield (FSY). The remaining factor was fixed at the center point value: 7.5%(w/w) (a) and 3.25h (b)

Fig. 2 FT-IR spectra of untreated and [Emim][OAc] pretreated rice straw

Fig. 3 SEM images of rice straw; **a-c:** untreated RS (x35, x180, x500), **d-f:** run 20 (70°C, 5%, 1.5h) (x35, x180, x500), **g-i:** run 7 (120°C, 5% solid loading, 5h) (x35, x180, x500), **j-l:** run 2 (137°C, 7.5% solid loading, 3.3h) (x35, x180, x500)

Fig. 4 XRD Patterns of untreated and [Emim][OAc] pretreated rice straw

Supplementary material: Optimization of rice straw pretreatment with 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate by the response surface method

Fig. S1 Calculated vs observed values of the developed model